

An Investigation into the Relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-Child Dynamics of Secondary Education Learner

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Received : 18/01/2025

1st BPR : 26/01/2025

2nd BPR : 07/02/2025

Accepted : 22/02/2025

Abstract

This study examines the correlation between Smart -phone addition and the Parent-child relationship among of Secondary education students with the increasing prevalence of Smartphone usage Concerns have emerged regarding its Potential impact on familial bonds and communication patterns. In this research, we used a quantitative correlational design to explore the relationship between the level of smartphone addiction and the quality of parent-child interactions. It concluded that there is no significant correlation between smartphone addiction and parent-child interactions, which led to the null hypothesis being accepted. This Suggests that smart-phone addiction does not directly affect the quality of Parent- child relationships within the sample Population. The Descriptive Survey research method is used in the Present study. This research method is most and widely used research design in education. Data is collected using Simple Random Sampling. The following tools have been used to collect the data for the study, "Parents-child relationship scale" (PCRS) by Late Nalini Rao and "Smart-phone Addiction scale (SAS)" by Dr. Vijay Shree and Dr. Mousad Ansari. The study highlights the importance of further research to understand other factors influencing Parent-child dynamics in the digital age recommendations include fostering healthy technology use and promoting open communication within families. The present study has been confined to students of Deoband, Saharanpur, District of Uttar Pradesh, India. For this reason, data from N=100 students is taken from different school in Deoband, Saharanpur, District of Uttar Pradesh, India.

Keywords: Smart-phone Addiction, Parents-child relationship, Secondary Education Students, Correlation Study.

Introduction

In today's era of modernization, technology has become an essential part of mundane life, particularly among teenagers. During this time, with these tools Providing access to information, communication and entertainment, their excessive use has raised concerns about potential negative effects on personal relationships. One area of concern is how smart-phone addiction may Influence the quality of Parent-child relationship. As Secondary education students spend Increasing amounts of time here on their Smart-phones, the dynamics of family communication and emotional connection may be affect. Parents-offspring relationships have a vital impact on the emotional and Social growth of adolescents. open Communication, trust, and quality, time together are fundamental in maintaining healthy family bonds. However, Excessive use of mobile phones can reduce children's interaction with family, increase misunderstandings, and create emotional distance. This raises the question of whether technology overuse significantly affects the quality of Parent-child relationships, particularly of among secondary education students who are at a turning point of personal and academic maturation.

Parent-child relationships play a crucial role in shaping adolescent behavior and emotional well-being. Warm and supportive interactions between parents and children promote healthy development, while inconsistent or neglectful parenting can foster risky behaviors, including excessive smartphone use (Shek et al., 2017). Studies suggest that when parents are preoccupied with their devices, adolescents may feel neglected, leading to emotional withdrawal and a greater reliance on smartphones for comfort and connection (Xie et al., 2018). Parental Pubbing and Its Consequences One significant issue related to smartphone addiction is parental pubbing, which refers to parents focusing on their smartphones while neglecting interactions with their children. This behavior can lead to feelings of neglect, reduced emotional connection, and increased behavioral problems in children (Xie et al., 2019). In contrast, inconsistent or overly strict mediation may contribute to increased aggression in children (Padilla-Walker et al., 2020). Effective interventions may include reducing parental screen time and encouraging quality family interactions to mitigate these adverse effects (Haidt, 2024).

Objectives of the Study

1. To Study the Smartphone Addiction of Secondary Education Students.
2. To study the Parent-child relationship of Secondary Education Students.
3. To study the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
4. To study the relationship between Compulsion Dimension of Smartphone Addition and Parent Child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
5. To study the relationship between Forgetfulness Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
6. To study the relationship between Lack of Attention Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
7. To study the relationship between Depression and Anxiety Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
8. To study the relationship between Disturbed Hunger/Sleep Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
9. To study the relationships between Social Withdrawal Dimension of Smartphone Addiction of Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.

Hypotheses of The Study:

1. There is no Significant Relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
2. There is no Significant Relationship between Compulsion Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
3. There is no Significant Relationship between Forgetfulness Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
4. There is no Significant Relationship between Lack of Attention Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.

5. There is no Significant Relationship between Depression and Anxiety Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
6. There is no Significant Relationship between Disturbed Hunger /Sleep Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.
7. There is no Significant Relationship between Social Withdrawal Dimension of Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary Education Students.

Methodology

Research Design : This study employs a non-experimental research to definitively examine the relationship between Smartphone addition and the parent-child relationship of secondary education students.

The Descriptive survey research method is used in the present study This research method in most important and widely used research design in Education A correlational approach is appropriate as it allows the researcher to measure the degree of association between two Variable- **Smartphone addiction (Independent Variable) and merits of the Parent-child relationship (Dependent variable).**
Population and Sampling : The population for this current study, is all 100 students of the Secondary Education Students from UP Board Deoband, located in Saharanpur District, Uttar Pradesh, India. The Target Population for this study consists of Secondary Education Students from selected schools, The Sample size is determined using Random Sampling to ensure that all Participants have an equal chance of being included, minimizing bias. The study includes student's aged 12 to 18 years old, as this age range represents the secondary education Level.

The Sample for the present study was taken from secondary schools of Deoband, Saharanpur District. These school were selected via Lottery system of Simple Random Sampling. Random Sampling Techniques was used for collecting the sample for the present study. The student was administered tests through Lottery system. In this present study, we have used the following tools: **1- Smart-Phone Addiction (SA) and 2- Parent-child Relationship (PCRS).**

Data analysis : To examine the data, the collected data has been analyzed using statistical approaches to determine the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship. Here we have used **Pearson's Product moment correlation coefficient (r)** to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child relationship.

Significance Level - AP-Value of ≤ 0.05 will be used to determine Statistical significance in either Supporting or rejecting the Null hypothesis.

In Pearson's Correlation, significance level is seen in Two ways, one at 0.05 level and one at 0.01 level.

Result/Interpretation

H1: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Smartphone Addiction and Parent-Child Relationship	-0.0261	NS

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 0261. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Smartphone addiction does not highly influence The parent's child relationship of the students. So, the null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Smartphone Addiction and Parent-child Relationship of secondary level students.

H2: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Compulsion Parent-Child and Relationship	-0.0482	NS

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 0482. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Compulsion does not highly influence The parents-child

relationship of the students. So, revealing the null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Compulsion and Parent-child Relationship of secondary level students.

H3: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Forgetfulness Parent Child and Relationship	-0.0027	N S

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 0027. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Forgetfulness does not highly influence The Parents-child Relationship of the students. Thus indicating the Null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Forgetfulness and Parent-child Relationship of secondary level Students.

H4: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Lack of Attention and Parent-Child Relationship	-0.038	N S

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 038. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Lack of Attention does not highly influence The Parents Child Relationship of the students. Here indicating the Null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Lack of Attention and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary level students.

H5: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Depression & Anxiety and Parent-Child Relationship	-0.048	N S

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 048. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Depression & Anxiety does not highly influence The Parents Child Relationship of the students. So, revealing the Null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Depression & Anxiety and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary level students.

H6: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Disturbed Hunger \ Sleep and Parent-Child Relationship	-0.024	N S

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is -0. 024. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Disturbed Hunger\Sleep does not highly influence The Parents-child Relationship of the students. Hence, the Null hypothesis has been accepted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Disturbed Hunger\Sleep and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary level students.

H7: The results obtained are given in below given table

Relationship Between	'r' Value	Level of Significance
Social Withdrawal and Parent-Child Relationship	0.088	N S

Obtained value of 'r' for hypothesis is 0.088. Thus there is Positive but negligible relationship between both variables. It means that Social withdrawal does not highly influence The Parents Child

Relationship of the students. Here revealing the Null hypothesis has been accepted. Hence it may be interpreted. Meaning there by no significant relationship between Social withdrawal and Parent-child Relationship of Secondary level students.

Conclusion

The main objective of this research is to "Study the relationship between smartphone addiction of secondary level students and parent-child relationships and also to study the correlation of variables in more depth". Since in today's modern era, it happens in the case of teenagers that they are highly dependent on technology all the time due to which they are letting smartphone addiction dominate them, therefore, there is a need for continuous and complete research on whether smartphone addiction is beneficial for students? Or this addiction has a negative impact on their parent-child relationship. Many prospective researchers have done research in this regard in the field of different populations. Where they found that both positive and negative correlations of smartphone addiction are present in parent-child relationships.

In this study the correlation design has been used because the researchers have studied relationship of Smart-phone Addiction and its components. This design illustrates how the Independent Variables (SA and its components) affect the Dependent variables (PCR).

From the analysis and statistical investigation of the above data, it is clear that smartphone addiction has a negative impact on the relationship between parents and children.

Suggestion for Further Study

When we conduct research in any area, all the aspects related to particulars study cannot be studied at a time due to limited resources and time at the end of the Investigation There may be certain important aspects which need to be studied for future clarity and understanding in that particular area of research. keeping this in mind, following suggestion are being offered for further research.

- 1 A similar can be conducted on large sample and different Districts students.
- 2 A study may be conducted on a sample drawn from different residential background.
- 3 A Study can be conducted on different groups, classified on the bases of Traits and Personality.
- 4 A study can be conducted to estimate the relationship of different aspects of Social Behavior influenced by the technology.
- 5 A study may be conducted to acknowledge the role of Smart-Phone usages in the context of academic achievement.
- 6 Present study was conducted on secondary level Student only. It may also be applied on graduate and Post Graduate students.
- 7 A Study of similar type may also the undertaken Focusing different streams Students, different Educational boards and different area also comparatively

Although the nomenclature as Gender, nature of College, stream and area in prevalent all over the Country, but these two aspects of students at different places and states of India have different result. So, in order to get a better picture of Some study should be conducted at different Geographical places.

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